

A new species of the genus *Helicopelta* Marshall, 1996 (Gastropoda: Addisoniidae) from the Norfolk Ridge (SW Pacific Ocean)

Una nueva especie del género *Helicopelta* Marshall, 1996 (Gastropoda: Addisoniidae) de la cresta de Norfolk (Pacífico SO)

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ABSTRACT

A new species belonging to the family Addisoniidae, from deep waters of the tropical Pacific, is described. It is compared with *Helicopelta rostricola* B. A. Marshall, 1996, the only previously known species of the genus *Helicopelta* B. A. Marshall, 1996 in the Pacific Ocean.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie perteneciente a la familia Addisoniidae procedente de aguas profundas del Pacífico tropical. Se compara con *Helicopelta rostricola* B. A. Marshall, 1996 única especie previamente conocida del género *Helicopelta* B. A. Marshall, 1996, del Océano Pacífico.

KEY WORDS: Gastropoda, Vetigastropoda, Addisoniidae, *Helicopelta*, Pacific, new species.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Gastropoda, Vetigastropoda, Addisoniidae, *Helicopelta*, Pacífico, nueva especie.

INTRODUCTION

During the study of a material with a preliminary identification as family Lyocyclidae in the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, from different Expeditions carried out by MNHN and IRD in the Indo-Pacific, we examined several specimens of a species, which although presenting a loosely disjunct teleoconch, differed from all the others examined in lacking axial lamellae, and above all, in the shape and ornamentation of the protoconch.

Thanks to the invaluable help of A. Warén (personal communication), we

found out that it was not a member of the Lyocyclidae, but rather an undescribed species of the genus *Helicopelta*, placed in the family Addisoniidae.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material used in this work was obtained during the NORFOLK 2 expedition, organized in 2003 by MNHN and IRD, in New Caledonia waters, on board R/V *Alis*, targeted to explore the seamounts of the Norfolk Ridge.

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Abbreviations
IRD Institut de Recherche pour le Dé-
veloppement

MNHN Museum National d'Histoire
Naturelle, Paris
Stn station
s empty shell

SYSTEMATICS

Order VETIGASTROPODA Salvini-Plawen, 1880
Family ADDISONIIDAE Dall, 1882
Subfamily HELICOPELTINAE B. A. Marshall, 1996
Genus *Helicopelta* B.A. Marshall, 1996

Helicopelta B.A. Marshall, 1996: 253 [Type species by monotypy: *Helicopelta rostricola* B.A. Marshall, 1996. New Caledonia. Recent].

Diagnosis (from MARSHALL, 1996): "Shell up to 1.90 mm wide, turbiniform, operculate; protoconch densely and minutely pitted, slightly tilted; teleoconch essentially smooth. Copulatory organ beside left cephalic tentacle, hemispherical (opening not detected); large gill comprising a row of leaflets centered left of body midline; cephalic tentacles without papillae; two posterior epipodial tentacles; shell muscle horseshoe-shaped, uninterrupted, very wide. Operculum thin, chitinous. Radula 11 + 5 + 1 + 5 + 11, central tooth scale-like, laterals 1-3 tile-like, lateral 4 small, lateral 5 and marginal 1 broadest, marginal 1 longest; lateral 5 with small cusp at inner end, broad outer part tightly interlocked with base of marginal 1. Marginal 1 with bluntly angulate or rounded cusps, marginal basal plates scale-like, outer marginal teeth (10 pairs) relatively very small, slender, cutting areas finely serrate. Internal anatomy unknown".

Remarks: MARSHALL (1996) wrote: "The type species of *Helicopelta* gen. nov. differs from all hitherto known members of the Cocculinoidea and Lepetelloidea in having an operculate coiled shell (as in Choristellidae) coupled with a shell muscle characteristic of a limpet, and in having the copulatory organ on the left side instead of the right. The radula uniquely combines central and lateral teeth similar to those of Addisoniidae with multiple marginal

teeth as in Cocculinoidea and Lepetelloidea with fully rhipidoglossate dentition (Cocculinidae, Pyropeltidae, Pseudococculinidae, Osteopeltidae), though the marginals are reduced in size and number and are evidently vestigial".

Therefore he concluded that *Helicopelta* is clearly referable to the Lepetelloidea rather than the Cocculinoidea. The only other members of the Lepetelloidea (or Cocculinoidea) with a coiled shell and that have an operculum in the adult stage are the Choristellidae (McLean, 1992). Choristellids differ in having jaws, a relatively small (left) shell muscle attached to the columella, and an essentially smooth protoconch, while a grooved right cephalic tentacle functions as the copulatory organ. *Addisonia* species differ in having a patelliform shell and the gill on the right side, and in that the right cephalic tentacle functions as the copulatory organ. Overall, MARSHALL (1996) found *Helicopelta* as different from all families and subfamilies of Lepetelloidea as those are from each other, which suggests that it may represent a family in its own right. Without a thorough re-evaluation of phylogenetic relationships within the superfamily and taking into account the unknown anatomy of *Helicopelta*, he conservatively allocated it as subfamily Helicopeltinae rank within Addisoniidae, associating it there solely on the basis of the similarity of the radula to that of *Addisonia*.

Helicopelta marshalli n. sp. (Fig. 1)

Helicopelta n. sp. in B.A. MARSHALL (1996: 253-254, figs. 9-12), immature specimens from off Southern New Caledonia, in 750 m.

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1A-B, MNHN-IM-2000-35752) in MNHN and 2 paratypes (MNHN-IM-2000-35753).

Material examined: 6 s: New Caledonia, NORFOLK 2: 3 s, Banc Éponge, Stn DW2086, 24°56'S-168°22'E, 707-777 m (type material); 3 s, Banc Jumeau est, Stn DW2054, 23°40'S-168°15'E, 736-800 m.

Type locality: New Caledonia, Banc Éponge, 24°56'S-168°22'E, 707-777 m [NORFOLK 2: DW2086].

Etymology: The specific name is after Dr. Bruce A. Marshall, New Zealand taxonomist and malacologist, who described the genus *Helicopelta* and figured, without giving them a name, two immature specimens of the new species described below.

Description: Shell very small (<2.10 mm in diameter), solid, lenticular, almost planispiral, with an obtuse spire formed by 2.2 loosely disjunct whorls.

Protoconch 200 µm wide, sharply delineated, of about 1/2 whorl, covered with minute, densely crowded, pits delimited by a sharp edge; and where unbraded, with stout columnar projections, with a flat top, next to each pit.

Teleoconch of about 1.5 loosely disjunct whorls, rapidly expanding; last half whorl is shifted abapically, developing below the previous whorl.

Ornamentation formed by very numerous growth lines that span the complete whorl.

Aperture oval to almost circular; peristome entire with a smooth edge. Outer lip slightly expanded. Umbilicus narrow and deep.

Dimensions: the holotype (Figs 1A-B) is 1.83 mm in diameter and the aperture has a maximum diameter of 1.15 mm; the paratypes are 2.01 and 1.96 mm in diameter and the shell of Fig. 1C-D is 1.97 mm in diameter (MNHN).

Animal unknown (dried). Operculum of juvenile specimens very thin, chitinous, colorless, spiral (MARSHALL, 1996).

Habitat: Bathyal species dredged between 707-800 m deep. The immature specimens examined by MARSHALL (1996) from southeast of New Caledonia, were alive on inner side of a pitted cephalopod beak deposited on the sea bottom.

Distribution: Only known from New Caledonia: southeast of New Caledonia,

Banc Éponge, Banc Jumeau, and from Banc Introuvable (the latter from CHALCAL2 sta. CP22, 24°40'S, 168°39'E, 650-750 m, reported by Marshall, 1996 as *Helicopelta* sp.).

Remarks: After a thorough comparative examination of our specimens with those described and figured by MARSHALL (1996) as *Helicopelta* sp., we have been able to verify that it is the same species (same protoconch and early teleoconch).

H. marshalli resembles *H. rostricola* in protoconch size, general appearance and opercular morphology, but it differs in having obtuse spire of loosely disjunct whorls. The protoconch surface is pitted exactly as in *H. rostricola*, but differs in that stout, nail-like columns project from the pits. Nothing like them has been previously recorded from Cocculinoidea or Lepetelloidea.

MARSHALL (1996: 254) wrote: "Judging from the fact that the columns are narrower than the pits and stuck to their sides, they seem likely to represent the dried, shrunken remains of an organic layer that is impervious to salts secreted during mineralization of the protoconch. The columns are clearly fragile and easily removed by abrasion. There is no trace of them on the protoconch of *H. rostricola*, and it is yet impossible to tell whether or not they were present and have since worn away. The similarities and the association with a cephalopod beak suggest that it is a species of *Helicopelta*, naming of which is withheld until better material is available".

Figure 1. *Helicopelta marshalli* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.01 mm in diameter, New Caledonia, Banc Éponge, NORFOLK 2 Stn DW2086, 707-777 m (MNHN); B, C: paratypes, 2.01 and 1.96 mm in diameter, same locality (MNHN); D: shell, 1.97 mm in diameter New Caledonia, East of Banc Jumeau, Stn DW2054, 736-800 m (MNHN); E, F: protoconch of the holotype and detail; G: protoconch of the shell of the figure D.

Figura 1. Helicopelta marshalli n. sp. A: *holotipo*, 2,01 mm de diámetro, Nueva Caledonia, Banc Éponge, NORFOLK 2 Stn DW2086, 707-777 m (MNHN); B, C: *paratipos*, 2,01 y 1,96 mm de diámetro, misma localidad (MNHN); D: *concha*, 1,97 mm de diámetro, Nueva Caledonia, al este del Banc Jumeau, Stn DW2054, 736-800 m (MNHN); E, F: *protoconcha* del *holotipo* y *detalle*; G: *protoconcha* de la *concha* de la *figura D*.

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